

ANALYSIS OF THE STATE OF DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL NETWORKS IN THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN

Rakhmatillaev Nodirjon Yo'ldashvaevich

National Institute of Metrology of Uzbekistan

deputy director of a state institution

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Abstract. In the article, suggestions and comments are mentioned in the case of studying the issues of large-scale work on the consistent development of industrial sectors in the regions, radical reform of industrial relations, modernization and diversification of production.

Key words: industrial products, industrial sectors, investment potential, capitalized investments, investment projects.

In order to diversify the industrial production in the regions of our country, in the 14 most important branches of industry, in particular, in the production of electric power, ferrous and non-ferrous metallurgy, oil and gas, chemistry, automobiles, cotton ginning, light industry, shoes, footwear, oil and pharmaceuticals, as well as in the production of construction products, modernization, technical and technological update programs have been adopted and implemented.

Measures aimed at strengthening the industrial potential and comprehensive development of regions in Uzbekistan and adopted in time served to create the necessary conditions for the development of industrial sectors at a stable pace. This was a positive factor for improving the quality of industrial production development. In recent years, the growth rate of industrial production has been high.

Manufacturing industry is a branch that includes physical or chemical processing of substances or components, materials, although not considered the only complete criterion for a certain type of production, in order to produce a new product. The volume of products produced by industrial enterprises in January-December 2023 is 553.3 trillion. soums or its share in the volume of total industrial products was 84.4%.

Compared to the corresponding period of last year, the share of the high-tech sector in the manufacturing industry is 1.4% (in January-December 2022 - 2.1%), medium-high technology - 24.8% (23, 1%, medium-low technology - 37.5% (36.8%), low-technology 36.3% (38.0%).

The share of production, repair and installation of machinery and equipment, production of motor vehicles, trailers, semi-trailers and other finished products in the total manufacturing industry is 22.4% (compared to

January-December 2022 physical volume index 107.4%), the share of the metallurgical industry - 22.8% (in comparison with January-December 2022, the physical volume index is 106.4%), the share of textile, clothing, leather products production - 17.4 % (physical volume index compared to January-December 2022 was 107.2%).

The share of the production of food, beverages and tobacco products in the manufacturing industry is 15.6% (the physical volume index is 105.9% compared to January-December 2022), the share of the production of chemical products, rubber and plastic products is 8.2% (in relation to January-December 2022, the physical volume index was 99.8%).

In January-December 2023, 1,333.1 thousand tons of automobile gasoline (increased by 6.0% compared to January-December 2022), 553.5 thousand tons of kalava yarn (decreased by 5.5%) were produced in the republic. 263.0 mln. liters of beer products (increased by 21.0%) and 1,128,000 tons of soft wheat and spelled flour (decreased by 35.1%) were produced.

Today, 69,400 industrial enterprises are operating in the republic, of which 11,800 (17.0% of the total number of registered enterprises) are in Tashkent, 7,800 (11.2%) are in Farg. to the mother region, 7.3 thousand (10.5%) to Tashkent region, 6.2 thousand (8.9%) to Samarkand region and 5.5 thousand (7.9%) to Andijan region.

As a result of systematic work aimed at modernization and diversification of industrial production and introduction of modern resource-saving technologies in our country, production of industrial products per capita is increasing significantly.

According to the types of economic activity, manufacturing industry, mining industry and exploitation of mines, supply of electricity, gas, steam and air condensation and water supply, sewage system, garbage collection and allocated to disposal networks.

The priority directions of structural change, modernization and diversification of industrial production in Uzbekistan are as follows:

1. Consistent modernization of production facilities operating in the field of electric power and creation of new ones based on widespread implementation of modern technologies that have been tested for the use of resource-saving steam-gas devices and solar energy.

2. To increase the production volume and expand the type of products with high added value based on the deep processing of natural gas and gas condensate in the oil and gas and petrochemical industry.

3. Diversification of production and export in the chemical industry by introducing modern technologies in the production of complex mineral fertilizers, polymers, synthetic rubber, methanol and a wide range of household chemical goods.

4. Establishment of new facilities for the production of import-substituting agricultural machinery, trucks and components in cooperation with technologically leading enterprises and expansion of existing enterprises.

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